

Evaluation Of Teachers' Assessment Practices in the Three Domains of Learning in Public Primary Schools In Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluated teachers' assessment practices in the three domains (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) of learning in public primary schools in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria. Three research questions were formulated to establish the proportion of teachers practicing assessments in the three domains of learning, the assessment tools and techniques often used by teachers in classroom assessment practices as measured in each domain of learning outcome and the domain/domains of learning outcomes teachers often assess pupils on. The design for the study was descriptive survey. The population of the study consisted of five thousand, five hundred and ninety-four (5,594) teachers from 503 public primary schools in Owerri Education Zone. Multi stage sampling procedure: simple random sampling, systematic random sampling and proportionate stratified random sampling techniques were used to select the sample. The sample for this study was 300 teachers consisting of 125 male and 175 female teachers. The instrument titled 'Teachers' Assessment Practices in the three Domains of Learning Questionnaire' (TAPDLQ) developed by the researchers was used for data collection. The TAPDLQ was face validated using three specialists in the field of Educational Evaluation. Copies of the questionnaire were trial tested on forty (40) teachers from public primary schools in Egbema Local Government Area, Rivers State and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha which yielded the internal consistency estimate of .86. Data collected for the study were analyzed using proportion, mean and standard deviation for research questions. The findings revealed that teachers often assess cognitive and affective domains but rarely use the assessment tools and techniques to assess the psychomotor domain. It was recommended that stakeholders in education should organize workshops and seminars for retraining of teachers on assessment procedures.

Keywords: *Assessment techniques, Bloom's taxonomy, Learning outcomes, teachers*

Introduction

Education brings positive change to learners. The extent of such change depends on the teachers who usually develop the scheme of work, plan with the national curriculum and objectives, organize learning materials and impart the knowledge to students (Ezechukwu et al, 2019). They also stipulate the skills and abilities necessary for maximum development of learners. Teachers employ practices that develop positive self-concept in pupils. Although the work of teachers typically takes place in a classroom setting, the direct interaction between teachers and pupils is the single most important element in teaching. The teacher is the essential element in the delivery of instructions to pupils, regardless of the mode of instruction. Teachers provide personal and caring services to students by diagnosing their needs and by planning, selecting and using methods and evaluation procedures designed to promote learning. How teachers can achieve these learning outcomes possess a problem. The teachers' role in achieving educational objectives is central because, though policies are beautifully articulated in terms of who does what and under what time frame the burden of executing the plan is still on the teachers. The teachers' inputs are indispensable to the attainment of the desired goals.

The goals of education will be better attained if quality delivery is rendered in primary schools in Nigeria. Quality deliveries of teaching in primary schools are critical for Nigeria to become globally competitive. It is only quality education that can sharpen the minds of the pupils and help transform the society. Such high quality educational provision enables citizens to acquire skills and techniques which are ploughed into human productivity, creativity, competence, initiative, innovation and inventiveness (Ehiametalor, 1988, as cited in Ezechukwu & Ukozor, 2019).

Primary schools in Nigeria offer teaching and learning for pupils to develop the intellectual capacities, empower them with the acquisition of physical and intellectual skills, to make them self-reliant and useful members of their society. Based on this, the Federal Government of Nigeria (2004) is guided in all of its activities by this vision, to produce national curriculum prescription, the application of which will produce individuals that can confront diverse life challenges effectively. This is in line with Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) stand, that primary education is fundamental to all developing countries, if they are to prosper in a world economy where knowledge has become a vital area of advantage.

Based on the desire of the National Policy on Education (2007) to foster quality learning among pupils, assessment, which measures how well learners have attained the learning outcomes (i.e. the Teacher's Standards) is considered pivotal in the new prescribed curriculum. Curriculum prescription represents the minimum content, materials and practices that would be expected by the primary schools in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The curriculum stipulates that Teacher educators need to know and use assessment procedures for learning and not just to gauge students' mastery of content or skills. Teacher ought to be strategic in the execution of appropriate methods. Their knowledge of assessment practices is important.

Assessment is a powerful educational tool. It is used to monitor the effectiveness of the system, evaluate education policies and programmes, make important instructional and placement decisions about pupils, and certify pupils' learning achievement. Assessment of pupils in the classroom practice is part and parcel of every teacher's activities and teachers who do not evaluate their own and their pupils' work cannot be said to be doing their job properly (Abe, 2004).

According to Dengsheny (2011), the word 'Assessment' comes from the root word assess which means to judge, or decide or determine the importance, size, or value of something. Assessment is a process used in collecting information on events and objects, particularly on human behaviour which is used to evaluate the quality of work done. Assessment is therefore the systematic process of gathering information from many sources to make appropriate educational decisions. It identifies the pupil's strengths, needs, weaknesses and contributes to the design and implementation of effective strategies. Teachers are in a position to offer an abundance of information regarding pupils in their classrooms. Informal assessments should form the basis of a comprehensive profile of pupils' strengths and challenges.

According to Ugodulunwa (2008), assessment is an integral and essential part of teaching and learning cycle. In the assessment process, there is a clear link between stated learning outcomes, the learning experiences the pupils are exposed to and the assessment tasks. Through assessment the teacher is able to diagnose pupils' learning difficulties and plan further instruction for them. Assessment can also be defined as skill that allows a teacher to infer pupil's understanding of concepts taught (Badders, 2011). In other words, assessment has to do with collecting data on pupils understanding of a concept in order to move the pupils' towards full understanding of more concepts.

Most often, assessment is carried out in full and not in part, meaning that assessment should be carried out in cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. Although the assessment strategies expected of teachers are not stated in the curriculum, the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) succinctly emphasized that 'educational assessment and evaluation shall be liberalized by their being in whole not in part'. It implies that the behaviour; attitude, interests, modes of interaction, skills, style of work and a variety of other non-cognitive factors will contribute to the decision made by the teacher on each pupil (Esere & Idowu, 2010). Furthermore, National Policy on Education (2004: 127 - 128) on Continuous assessment states that an assessment approach should involve the use of a variety of assessment instruments, assessing various components of learning, not only the thinking processes but including behaviours, personality traits and manual skillfulness. Assessment should be objective, systematic, comprehensive, cumulative and guidance oriented (Idowu & Esere, 2009). By being comprehensive, it implies that assessment should consider all the various aspects of the child's development (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) in the overall assessment of the pupil's performance according to Bloom's taxonomy of learning.

Learning outcomes are the domains of cognitive, according to Iwuji (2010) and have direct bearing to reasoning operations. They are concerned with mental abilities to understand things and think

intelligently. Researchers such as Huilt (2003); Halpern, (2004); Udoukpong and Okon, (2012) opined that intellectual activities have varying degrees of complications and levels in learning. This presupposes that teachers should use their lessons to enhance the development of intellectual abilities of their pupils to the highest level of reasoning, not just recall of specific facts.

Bloom's taxonomy is a multi-tiered model of classifying thinking according to the six cognitive levels of complexity. Throughout the study period, the levels have often been depicted as a stairway, leading many teachers to encourage their pupils to 'climb to higher levels of thought'. The lowest three levels are: Knowledge, comprehension, and application. The highest three levels are: analysis, synthesis and evaluation (Idowu & Esere, 2009). Each level is preceded by the next higher level. In other words, a pupil functioning at the application level must have mastered the materials at the knowledge and comprehension levels.

Learning domains are: Cognitive: Mental skills (knowledge), consisting of six levels. This domain focuses on intellectual skills and is familiar to teachers. Knowledge –ability to remember facts without necessarily understanding. Comprehension is the ability to understand and interpret learned information. Application – ability to use learned materials in new situations. Analysis – ability to break down information into its components. Synthesis – ability to put parts together and Evaluation is the ability to judge value of material for a given purpose. Measuring cognitive learning outcomes will involve all the intellectual aspects of behaviour. To evaluate these, one would be looking out for evidence or manifestation of such skills in comprehension, critical and creative thinking, organizing, analyzing, interpreting and generalizing in problem solving, questioning etc. To evaluate these, instruments needed are; assignments, quizzes, tests, essay/objective, homework and class work (Harbor-Peters in Acholonu, 2014). Tests are the most commonly used instrument for assessing cognitive learning outcomes. There are standardized test which include intelligence and diagnostic tests as well as teacher made tests. Teacher made tests are periodically used for measuring learning outcome in the process of education.

Affective: This domain according to Sotote and Iyamu (2006) focuses on feelings, emotions and attitudes. It consists of five levels: Receiving - willing to listen; Responding -active participation of the learner; Valuing is the ability to see the worth of something and express it; Organizing - ability to prioritize a value over another and create a unique value system; Characterization - willing to change one's behaviour, lifestyle, or way of life. These stages are not as sequential as the cognitive domain. To measure affective learning outcomes, tools needed include observation, Guess-who by peers, Anecdotal records, Checklists, interviews and Sociometric technique (Harbor-Peters in Acholonu, 2014).

Psychomotor: Psychomotor domain focuses on performing sequences of motor activities to a specified level of accuracy, smoothness, rapidity, or force. Below are the seven levels in psychomotor domain: Perception; Senses cues that guided motor activity. Uses sense organs to obtain cues to guide action: ranges from awareness of stimulus to translating cue perception into action. Sentimentally, emotionally and physically ready to act. Readiness to take action; includes mental, physical and emotional

sets: mentally, emotionally and physically ready to act. Guided response; imitates and practices skills, often in discrete steps. Knowledge of the steps required to perform a task: includes imitation and trial and error. Mechanism; performs acts with increasing, efficiency, confidence and proficiency. Perform tasks in a habitual manner: with a degree of confidence and proficiency. Complex overt; response performed automatically. Skill performance of motor acts involving complex patterns of Movement, Adaptation; adapts skill to meet a problem situation. Modifies movement patterns to account for problematic or new situations: Origination; creates new patterns for specific situations. Creating new movement patterns to account for problematic or new situations; creates new tasks that incorporate learned ones. The tools needed to measure psychomotor aspects of behaviour include: Observation, Classwork, Assignment, Project, Questionnaire and Homework (Harbor-Peters in Acholonu, 2014).

One of the major roles of teachers in the teaching-learning encounter is to assess pupils' learning. This mostly comes in form of tests of educational achievement. The assessment of educational achievement is probably the most important event of the educational system. It haunts the child from the day he enters a nursery school and culminates to his adulthood. How it is practiced therefore is of concern to every Nigerian. Decisions based on tests results are important for they measure suitable learning outcomes. Empirical evidence on learning outcomes measured by the teacher-made tests has shown that teacher-made tests are mostly centered on the cognitive domain (Carlo, 2003; Merid, 2002). Merid study of tests from 250 pupils' from 25 public and 15 private primary schools in Ethiopia showed 16.5% and 15.2% difference between the aim of test item and the expected outcomes in the syllabus in public and private primary schools respectively and that the test measured knowledge and comprehension. Studies by Crooks in Hamman-Tukur and Atsua (2016) and Stiggins and Griswold, 1998 in Hamman-Tukur and Atsua (2016) revealed that teachers have difficulty in assessing complex abilities such as writing or Mathematical problem solving.

In conducting the assessment, the teachers should state clearly the objectives or learning outcomes at each of the stated levels in the three domains before evaluation and should be fully conversant with the instruments for measuring the stated learning outcomes. The teacher is also expected to possess the skills for designing these tools and administering them. Unfortunately, some of the teachers' test items for measuring cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning outcomes are sometimes not well constructed, because majority of teachers do not have the expertise to carry out continuous assessment in the affective and psychomotor domains (Unachukwu & Onunkwo, 2004; Akinsola, 2006). Studies by searchers Ugodulunwa and Mastapha (2005) and Opoola (2006) showed that many teachers in primary schools in Owerri Municipal Council, Imo State are incompetent in conducting effective and efficient assessment of learners' achievement, do not know how to construct and use appropriate instrument to assess teachers' practices in assessment of the three domains of learning.

Furthermore, researchers have shown that teacher-made tests are flawed and characterized by the following: have about 80% of their items constructed at the lower level of Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive objectives, use of short and ambiguous items, grammatical errors and lack of direction among others

(Oescher & Kirby, 1995 as cited in Wakjissa, 2018; Wakjissa, 2011). Rahman and Ahmed (2010) in their work found that teachers do not have enough methods of assessing their pupils. To maintain standard, a complete assessment must cover all the three domains of educational objectives - cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains (Okpala et al, 2006). Akinsola (2007) and James (2007) concluded that the implementation of Assessment in three domains poses some serious challenges and that most teachers do focus on cognitive domain without paying attention to other domains. For education to meet the demand of society, it must ensure the development of all three domains among learners.

Effective and efficient assessment of learners' achievements in various subjects has been a recurring problem to education planners and administrators. It has been discussed in many seminars, conferences and workshops. The assessment of educational achievement is probably the most important aspect of the educational system. Researchers have shown that, teacher made tests are flawed as about 80% of their items are constructed at the lower level of Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive objectives. To maintain standard, an efficient and effective assessment must cover all the three domains of educational objectives - cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Therefore, the purpose of the study is to evaluate teachers' assessment practices in the three domains of learning in public primary schools in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of Study

The general purpose of the study is to evaluate teachers' assessment practices in the three domains of learning in public primary schools in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study sought to:

- a. identify the proportion of teachers practicing assessments in the three domains of learning.
- b. Determine the assessment tools and techniques often used by teachers in classroom assessment practices as measured in each domain of learning outcome.
- c. ascertain the domain/domains of learning outcomes teachers often assess pupils on.

Research Questions

In carrying out this study, three research questions were formulated for this study.

1. What proportion of teachers are practicing assessments in the three domains of learning?
2. What are the assessment tools and techniques often used by teachers in classroom assessment practices as measured in each domain of learning outcome?
3. Which domain/domains of learning outcomes do teachers often assess pupils in?

Methods

The research design adopted for the study was descriptive survey. According to Kpolovie (2010), survey research design requires a collection of a wide variety and large volume of data that are quantitative or that are quantifiable and analyzes them with different types of complex statistics for arriving at dependable answers to the research questions and testing of the tenability of the postulated hypotheses. With the research questions answered and hypotheses tested, appropriate and clear interpretations are given to

adequately meet the purpose of the study. This design is considered appropriate for this study by the researchers. Three research questions were used for the study.

The study was carried out in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria. The Zone is made up of nine (9) local government areas. The population of the study consisted of five hundred and ninety-four (5,594) teachers from 503 public primary schools in Owerri, Imo State (State Universal Basic Education Board (2019/2020)). The sample for this study was 300 teachers. The sample was selected through a multi stage sampling technique. Firstly, a simple random sampling technique was used to draw five local government areas in Owerri Education Zone. Secondly, a simple random sampling through balloting was used to draw six primary schools each from the randomly selected Local Government Areas, that is, 30 primary schools. Thirdly, in each of the selected primary schools, systematic random sampling was used to draw 10 teachers, totaling 300 teachers. At the fourth stage, 300 teachers made of 175 male and 215 female were drawn through proportionate stratified random sampling technique, hence, the sample for this study was 300 teachers made of 125 male and 175 female teachers selected from middle basic education.

The instrument titled ‘Teachers’ Assessment Practices in the three Domains of Learning Questionnaire’ (TAPDLQ) was used for data collection. The TAPDLQ consists of four sections, section A, B, C and D. Section A was on bio-data of teachers. Section B is on proportion of the teachers that are practicing assessment in the three domains of learning, section C dealt with 21 items on the assessment tools and techniques often used by teachers in classroom assessment practices as measured in each domain of learning outcome and section D consisted of 17 items on domain/domains of learning outcomes teachers often assess pupils. The total no of items on the questionnaire is 41. TAPDLQ was arranged on a 4-point Likert scale of Often, Sometimes, Rarely and Never.

The TAPDLQ was face validated using three specialists from the field of Educational Evaluation. Copies of the questionnaire were trial tested on forty (40) teachers from middle basic schools in Egbema local government area in Rivers State and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha which yielded the internal consistency estimates of .86. TAPDLQ was administered to the teachers in their respective schools. Two research assistants were employed and trained to help the researchers in the administration of TAPDLQ. Data collected were analyzed using percentages, mean and standard deviation for research questions. The researchers used a criterion mean of 2.50 as the benchmark for decision making. Means value of 2.50 and above were agreed while mean values below 2.50 were disagreed.

Results

Table 1. Proportion of Teachers Practicing Assessment in the three Domains of Learning

S/N	Item Statement	Practice		Not Practice	
	In assessing pupils, I give tasks to cover the following domains of learning:	N	%	N	%
1.	Cognitive Domain	300	100	0	0
2.	Affective Domain	112	37.33	188	62.66

3.	Psychomotor Domain	125	41.66	175	58.33
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Data in Table 1 shows that all the 300 teachers practice assessment in the cognitive domain. However, 112 representing 37.33% practice assessment in the affective domain, while 125 representing 41.66% practice assessment in the psychomotor domain.

Table 2: Teachers Response on how often they use assessment tools and techniques N = 300

S/N	Item Statement	\bar{X}	Std
Assessment tools and techniques used by the teachers:			
Cognitive Instrument			
1	Assignments	3.21	0.76
2	Quizzes	1.74	0.78
3	Tests	3.03	0.71
4	Essay and objective	2.95	0.79
5	Homework	2.94	0.81
6	Class work	2.56	0.88
Affective Instrument			
8	Observation method	3.06	0.88
9	Guess-who by peers	1.99	0.96
10	Anecdotal records	1.37	0.67
11	Checklist	2.34	1.04
12	Sociometric technique	2.22	0.95
13	Interview	1.81	0.93
Psychomotor			
15	Practical skills test	2.21	0.97
16	Project	2.72	0.91
17	Communication skills test	2.96	0.96
18	Examination	3.51	0.68
19	Questionnaire	1.87	0.73
20	Home work	2.94	0.81
21	Speed test	2.32	0.96
Cluster Mean		2.27	

Table 2 showed that the assessment tools employed by the teachers for assessment in the cognitive domain of learning are assignments, tests, essay and objective, homework and classwork. These tools have mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. In the affective domain, the only assessment tool employed by the teachers is observation method. On the other hand, the teachers employed project, communication skills test, examination, and homework as assessment tools for assessing the psychomotor domain.

Table 3: Teachers' response to the behaviours often assessed

S/N	Item statement	\bar{X}	Std
Cognitive Domain			
1	Prior knowledge	3.12	0.86
2	Understanding	2.97	1.02
3	Problem solving	2.68	0.83
4	Critical thinking	2.37	0.86
5	Creative thinking	2.01	0.85
6	Evaluation skill	1.80	0.97
Affective Domain			

7	Attitude	3.05	0.91
8	Self-awareness	3.12	0.86
9	Learning skills	3.27	0.7
10	Pupils' reactions to teaching and learning	2.96	0.96
11	Pupils' reactions to fellow pupils	2.77	0.93
12	Pupils' reactions when placed in groups	2.77	0.93
13	Pupils' reactions when assessing the work of their peers (peer assessment)	2.52	1.01
Psychomotor Domain			
14	Perceptual abilities	2.98	0.92
15	Communication skill	2.96	0.96
16	Decision making skill	2.19	0.98
17	Problem solving skill	2.30	0.84
Cluster Mean		2.69	

Table 3 showed that the levels of cognitive domain assessed by the teachers are those in items 1, 2 and 3, which have mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. These levels of cognitive domain are prior knowledge, understanding, and problem solving. All the aspects of affective domain were assessed by the teachers. On the other hand, the aspects of psychomotor domain assessed by the teachers are perceptual abilities, and communicative skills.

Discussion

The result from Table 1 on proportion of Teachers Practicing Assessment in the three Domains of Learning in public primary schools in Owerri Education Zone, Imo State, Nigeria shows that 100% of teachers practice assessment in the cognitive domain. However, 37.33% practice assessment in the affective domain, while 41.66% practice assessment in the psychomotor domain. This agrees with the view of Carlo, (2003) and Merid, (2002) study on learning outcomes that teacher-made tests are mostly centered on the cognitive domain. Thus, it is correct to state that teachers mostly assess the cognitive domain to the neglect of the affective and psychomotor domains.

The finding in Table 2 showed that the assessment tools employed by teachers for assessing the cognitive domain of learning are assignments, tests, essay and objective, homework and classwork. These tools have mean rating scores above the criterion mean of 2.50. This is in line with researchers who have shown that teacher-made tests are flawed and characterized by the following: have about 80% of their items constructed at the lower level of Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive objectives, use of short and ambiguous items, grammatical errors and lack of direction among others (Oescher & Kirby, 1995 as cited in Wakjissa, 2018; Wakjissa, 2011). In the affective domain, the only assessment tool employed by the teachers is observation method. This is consistent with the view of Ahmed (2010) who found that teachers do not have enough methods of assessing their pupils in affective domain. On the other hand, the teachers employed project, communication skills test, examination, and homework as assessment tools for assessing the psychomotor domain. This is consistent with the reports of studies by Crooks in Hamman-Tukur and Atsua

(2016) and Stiggins and Griswold, 1998 in Hamman-Tukur and Atsua (2016) revealed that teachers have difficulty in assessing complex abilities such as writing.

Table 3 showed that the levels of cognitive domain assessed by the teachers are prior knowledge, understanding, and problem solving. These findings agree with Unachukwu and Onunkwo, 2004 that teachers assess only some aspects of the domain especially the cognitive domain. All the aspects of affective domain are assessed by the teachers. The finding is not in consonance with Ugodulunwa and Mastapha (2005) and Opoola (2006) who showed that many teachers are incompetent in conducting effective and efficient assessment in affective domain of learners' achievement. On the other hand, the aspects of psychomotor domain assessed by the teachers are perceptual abilities, and communicative skills. This is not in line with the observations of Sotote and Iyamu (2006) that primary school teachers are competent enough to set psychomotor instruments in assessment.

Conclusions

From the findings, it was shown that teachers assess most aspect of the cognitive domain to the neglect of most aspects of the affective and psychomotor domains. The findings also showed that the assessment tools employed by the teachers for assessing the cognitive domain of learning are assignments, tests, essay and objective, homework and classwork while in affective domain, the only assessment tool employed by the teachers is observation method. On the other hand, the teachers employed project, communication skills, test, examination, and homework as assessment tools for assessing the psychomotor domain. However, these assessment tools employed by the teachers are higher in the cognitive and psychomotor domains than the affective. The implication of these finding is that Nigeria primary schools are likely to witness improvement in the assessment tools employed by the teachers for assessing both cognitive and psychomotor domains of learning. However, there will be lapses in the assessment tools employed by the teachers for assessing affective domain as the teachers appear to be lagging behind.

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government and relevant educational stakeholders should continue to make more effort to afford teachers the opportunity to improve their knowledge through workshops and seminars for training and retraining of teachers.
2. Teachers should endeavour to often use the assessment tools and techniques in all three domains of assessment so that all the required behaviours in the learner will be assessed.
3. The government should provide primary schools with the necessary facilities to facilitate learning in the three domains.

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